

D1.3 Innovation Management Plan

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Abstract

Key words

Innovation, exploitation, stakeholders, engagement, key exploitable results, intellectual properties

The document guides the planning, development, and implementation of IRISCC innovations, optimizing resources and processes to foster growth and competitiveness. It also ensures all project results are systematically captured, assessed for exploitation readiness, and validated along with an improvement cycle to strengthen them.

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Terminology/Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
ACTRIS	Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure
AnaEE	Analysis and Experimentation of Ecosystems
CA	Consortium Agreement
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CEPF	Confederation of European Forests Owners
CtA	Call to Action
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication
DoA	Description of Action
DRMKC	The European Commission Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EEA	European Environment Agency
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EIRENE	Environmental Exposure Assessment Research Infrastructure
EMBRC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre
EMS	Emergency Management Service
ENVRI	Environmental Research Infrastructures
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
ESA	European Space Agency
EURATOM	European Atomic Energy Community
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GESIS	Leibniz Institute for the Social Science
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
HE	Horizon Europe
IAGOS	In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
IP	Intellectual Property
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights

IS-ENES	European Network for Earth System Modelling
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OPTED	Observatory for Political Texts in European Democracies
R&I	Research & Innovation
RA	Remote Access
RI	Research Infrastructure
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SeaDataNet	Pan-European infrastructure for ocean & marine data management
TA	Transnational Access
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VA	Virtual Access
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, Critical Zone and Socio-ecological Research Infrastructure
Zenodo	EU Open Research Repository

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Executive Summary

This document serves as the project's Innovation Management plan, designated as Deliverable D1.3. It outlines the specific measures the project will employ for innovation, but also engagement among stakeholders. These measures aim to ensure the project's maximum impact, both throughout its duration and beyond.

To guarantee the IRISCC project's utilisation by the Grant Agreement, the innovation management system and all its associated plans and processes activities are described in this deliverable. The deliverable describes how the context will be evaluated, how the main exploitable findings and results will be gathered, and how the relevant exploitation and business planning activities will be monitored. Target groups and project stakeholders will be included in conjunction with the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication plan to maximise and guarantee project uptake.

The primary processes, role templates, information to be gathered, plan and timeframe for implementing the system, baseline, and early progress from the first few months are all described in this document together with the innovation management system.

Follow-up progress will be presented as a component of the Deliverable D1.5 IRISCC policy brief I, and its updates, as well as in reports and white papers.

This revised version (v2.0) updates and strengthens the original Innovation Management Plan (v1.0) by providing a more operational description of the innovation management framework. In particular, it clarifies the procedures for identifying, reviewing, validating, and updating Project Results, Intellectual Property (IP), Key Exploitable Results (KERs), exploitation plans, sustainability analyses, and impact-related information throughout the project lifecycle. It also further specifies the roles and responsibilities involved in these processes, including the Innovation Manager, Work Package (WP) Leaders, Task Leaders, KER Champions, consortium partners, and the Executive Board. In addition, v2.0 introduces a clearer timeline and review cycle and better explains how innovation management activities are integrated with reporting, monitoring, dissemination, exploitation, sustainability, and governance processes, ensuring that innovation management is implemented systematically rather than as a parallel activity.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

In the context of Work Package (WP) 1 - Co-design of IRISCC integrated knowledge services, Task 1.1 - Project Communication and Dissemination strategy and its implementation focuses on Communication and Dissemination, Task 1.2 - Stakeholder mapping and engagement on Stakeholder Engagement and Task 1.3 - Promotion of the IRISCC Catalogue of services on promotion of the IRISCC Service Catalogue and Task 1.4 - Innovation Management and Exploitation on Exploitation and Innovation management activities. The present Deliverable outlines a comprehensive plan for the Innovation and Exploitation tasks, aligning them with target audiences and stakeholders as they are presented in the Deliverables D1.1 (Stakeholder mapping and analysis) [R1] and D1.2 (Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) strategy) [R2], establishing a timeline where feasible, and identifying key success indicators.

The project's innovation management system is addressed by the actions listed in this plan. It contains the plan's description, relevant processes, anticipated activities, and the forms required to gather data while the project is being carried out.

The plan detailed in this Deliverable aims to effectively make sure that project results are identified, documented and evaluated to determine how well they fit into the political, technological, and commercial context. It also organises the exploitation activities to make sure the findings are developed further and used once the project is finished. This Innovation Management Plan (D1.3) outlines how the project outcomes, including the Key Exploitable Results (KER), will be recorded, tracked, and utilised. Along with the first progress in some of the activities pertinent in the first few months, this deliverable also offers the baseline for the expected outcomes, key exploitable results, and exploitation strategies as they were anticipated in the Description of Action (DoA) and in the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) Plan (D1.2, R2).

This document provides templates to give a consistent and organised method for addressing the actions pertaining to exploitation, sustainability, impact, and IP management. They will be updated following the specific needs identified during the project and they are supplied in the appendixes.

The Innovation Management Plan is dynamic and subject to updates throughout the project lifespan, with adjustments made based on project progress: adjustment to the plans, any new processes or updates to templates will be incorporated. Tailored outreach initiatives and engagement approaches will be devised for each stakeholder group,

considering their specific needs, work package activities, and expected levels of engagement. This plan will receive an update that will be included in the “Updated version of the DEC strategy” in M24 (D1.6) as well as in the periodic reports.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The document is organised as follows:

- The first chapter gives a basic overview of the situation, including duties and responsibilities as well as necessary definitions so that everyone is aware of what is expected of them.
- The project’s methodology for evaluating how innovation is moving towards exploitation and sustainability is outlined in the second chapter.
- The third chapter is devoted to IPR management and exploitation.
- The innovative processes are described in the fourth chapter.
- The baseline status of the IRISCC Key Exploitable Results is given in the fifth chapter.
- The sixth chapter contains the conclusions.
- There are templates in the annexes.

1.3 Framework and Context

Task 1.4 of WPI of the IRISCC DoA outlines the goal of the Innovation Management Plan as a Pathway from KERs to maximal exploitation leading to innovation with a description of innovation management. This work is built on the EGI knowledge of innovation management developed through projects such as interTwin, EOSC-HUB etc. It describes tasks whose completion the Innovation Management plan is expected to guide and ensure, and it comprises the following when defining an Innovation Management System:

- The Innovation Process as a Pathway to Impact concept highlights the need for systematic and efficient management of the innovation process to have a significant impact.
- Operational Innovation Management Implementation (T1.4):
 - the plan creates an operational innovation management process to record project outcomes in an organised manner, and
 - evaluates the results’ suitability for exploitation and verifies them using a cycle of improvement.
- Support for WPI’s Strategy:
 - It backs the plan of exploitation.
 - Keeps an eye on how well diffusion efforts are working.
 - Monitors changes in the external environment to find new chances for exploitation and to react to feedback.
- Finding and Outlining the Key Exploitable Results (KERs):
 - The plan explains KERs and their potential for exploitation, as well as approaches to intellectual property rights (IPR) and the essential steps for dissemination.

- Makes certain that every KER is enhanced and optimised for maximum impact.
- KER Champions, Task Partners who:
 - Will actively collaborate with all pertinent work packages (WPs) to advance and improve KERs.
- Project Sustainability Contribution (T7.4):
 - The plan finds alternate business plans to guarantee the services' long-term viability.

The main IRISCC deliverables interconnected with the previous list of activities are:

- D1.2 DEC Strategy (, Egi.eu)
- D1.3 Innovation Management Plan (this document).

A comprehensive review of all other deliverables from the technical work packages (from WP2 to WP11) will aid in obtaining a comprehensive screening of all the technologies, building blocks, and services produced throughout the project as defined in the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement.

1.4 Roles and Responsibilities

An assigned Innovation Manager is responsible for carrying out the activities under task 1.4 within the Project. In the Table 1 - Tasks and Responsibilities all the roles and responsibilities are listed for a comprehensive understanding and efficient collaboration.

The roles described in Table 1 are operationally implemented throughout the innovation management processes described in Chapter 4. The Innovation Manager is assigned at project start within Task T1.4, while Process Managers and Task Leaders are identified according to the specific innovation management processes and activities. WP Leaders and Task Leaders contribute to the identification, review, and validation of Project Results and KERs within their respective domains. KER Champions are designated during the KER Management process based on the relevance of the identified results and the expertise of the involved partners. Governance-related validation activities are performed by the Executive Board during major reporting activities and governance reviews.

Table 1. Tasks and Responsibilities

Role	Tasks/Responsibilities	Staff assigned
Innovation Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying Exploitable Results: Identifying and cataloguing all potentially exploitable results of IRISCC, including new knowledge, technologies, products, services, and processes developed during the project. • Developing an Exploitation Strategy: Crafting a comprehensive exploitation plan that outlines how project results will be utilised, 	1 for the Innovation Manager, the project Innovation Manager [Elia Bellussi]

	<p>including potential markets, stakeholders, and pathways for commercialisation or further development.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IP Management: Ensuring that intellectual property (IP) generated during the project is properly protected and managed, including handling patents, copyrights, trademarks, and other forms of IP. • Reporting and Documentation: Preparing detailed reports on exploitation activities and progress, including contributions to official deliverables and updates to exploitation plans as required by the project's funding body. • Coordination with Consortium Partners: Coordinating exploitation activities across consortium partners, ensuring that each partner's exploitation interests are considered and that there is a cohesive strategy for the use of project results. • Monitoring and Evaluation: Monitoring the effectiveness of exploitation activities and adjusting strategies as necessary to maximise impact. This might include assessing the commercial viability of outcomes and tracking their adoption in the market. • Compliance and Ethics: Ensuring that exploitation activities comply with relevant legal, ethical, and regulatory requirements, particularly concerning IP management and commercialisation. • Capacity Building: Facilitating training and capacity-building activities for project partners to enhance their ability to exploit the project results effectively. • Communication and Dissemination: Working closely with communication and dissemination teams to align these activities with exploitation goals, ensuring that project results reach the right audiences. 	
Process Managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serves as the primary contact point for questions and concerns regarding an Innovation Management process from a governance and operational perspective. 	1 per process (See assigned staff in the Innovation

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defines scope and goals for a process, nominates the process staff, identifies collaborators, and agrees with them on how the process should be developed. • Define the scope and goals for an activity and identify collaborators in collaboration with the Innovation Management process manager. • Serve as the primary contact point for questions and concerns regarding an Innovation Management process activity from an operational perspective. • Determines the process implementation plan, in collaboration with the Innovation Management manager, and process staff managers, and keeps track of its development. • Coordinates the work page staff working on the process in regular meetings. • Proposes changes for the process after monitoring and reviewing, in collaboration and agreement with the process staff, and requests approval by the Innovation Management manager. • Reports and, if necessary, escalate any issues impeding the process implementation to the Innovation Management manager. • Participates in internal and external meetings to represent and develop the KERs. 	Management process overview)
Process staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If needed, people from the related work packages working on the process tasks will perform activities following the Task leader's instructions and, if applicable, the processes defined (e.g. how to document a project result). • Report to the task responsible. 	As needed
Project result contact	Process staff who perform the following tasks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individuals who serve as the primary contact for a project result, encouraging its adoption, exploitation and dissemination. • Support the Results Management process manager in collecting the information related to the results and bridge the gap between technical outputs and their practical implications by promoting uptake. 	1 per result (See process Results Management)

KER Champion	Process staff who perform the following tasks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serve as the primary representative of a KER, encouraging its adoption, exploitation and dissemination. • Support the KERs Management process manager in collecting the information related to the results and bridge the gap between technical outputs and their practical implications by promoting uptake. 	1 per KER (See process KER Management)
WP Leaders/Task Leaders	Process staff who perform the following tasks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribute to the identification, review, and validation of Project Results and candidate KERs within their respective Work Packages and Tasks. • Support the collection and update of innovation-related information, including exploitation, sustainability, and impact contributions. • Collaborate with the Innovation Manager and KER Champions during review activities and governance checkpoints. • Contribute to the definition of exploitation opportunities, sustainability analyses, and impact pathways related to their technical domains. • Support periodic reporting and validation activities related to innovation management processes. 	1 per Work Package/Task.
Executive Board	Process staff who perform the following tasks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide governance oversight and strategic validation for innovation management activities. • Review and validate candidate KERs, exploitation priorities, sustainability strategies, and impact-related activities. • Support prioritisation decisions related to innovation opportunities, exploitation readiness, and strategic alignment with project objectives. • Review progress during governance meetings, reporting activities, and major deliverable submissions. • Support the resolution of conflicts or strategic issues related to innovation management, IP, exploitation, and sustainability activities. 	Members defined in the project governance structure and Consortium Agreement.

1.5 Definitions

The keywords "MUST", "MUST NOT", "REQUIRED", "SHALL", "SHALL NOT", "SHOULD", "SHOULD NOT", "RECOMMENDED", "MAY", and "OPTIONAL" in this document are to be interpreted as described in [RFC 2119](#) [R3].

The development of a successful DEC strategy, as well as the Innovation Management Plan, is contingent upon the establishment of a precise list of keywords.

The keywords listed in Table 2 are the cornerstone of ensuring that all communication and dissemination endeavours are strategically aligned with the intended target audiences, including academic researchers, policymakers, potential investors, and industry stakeholders.

Keywords are crucial in emphasising the innovations' fundamental value propositions and distinctive characteristics in the context of the innovation management process.

Table 2. Definitions related to Exploitation

Definition	Description	Reference
Access rights for entities under the same control	<p><i>Unless agreed otherwise in writing by the beneficiaries, access to results and, subject to the restrictions referred to above (if any), background must also be granted – under fair and reasonable conditions – to entities that:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Are established in an EU Member State or Horizon Europe-associated country,</i> <i>are under the direct or indirect control of another beneficiary, or the same direct or indirect control as that beneficiary, or directly or indirectly controlling that beneficiary and</i> <i>need access to exploit the results of that beneficiary.</i> <p><i>Unless agreed otherwise in writing, such access requests must be made by the entity directly to the beneficiary concerned.</i></p> <p><i>Access requests must be made – unless agreed otherwise in writing – up to one year after the end of the action (see Data Sheet, Point 1).</i></p>	IRISCC Grant Agreement
Access rights for exploiting the results	<p><i>The beneficiaries must grant each other access – under fair and reasonable conditions – to the results needed for exploiting their results.</i></p> <p><i>The beneficiaries must grant each other access – under fair and reasonable conditions – to the</i></p>	IRISCC Grant Agreement

	<p><i>background needed for exploiting their results unless the beneficiary that holds the background has – before acceding to the Agreement – informed the other beneficiaries that access to its background is subject to restrictions. Access requests must be made – unless agreed otherwise in writing – up to one year after the end of the action (see Data Sheet, Point 1).</i></p>	
<p>Access rights for implementing the action</p>	<p><i>The beneficiaries must grant each other access – on a royalty-free basis – to background needed to implement their tasks under the action, unless the beneficiary that holds the the background has – before acceding to the Agreement:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• informed the other beneficiaries that access to their background is subject to restrictions, or</i> <i>• agreed with the other beneficiaries that access would not be on a royalty-free basis.</i> <p><i>The beneficiaries must grant each other access – on a royalty-free basis – to results needed for implementing their tasks under the action.</i></p>	<p>IRISCC Grant Agreement</p>
<p>Access rights for the granting authority, EU institutions, bodies, offices or agencies and national authorities to results for policy purposes – Horizon Europe actions</p>	<p><i>In Horizon Europe actions, the beneficiaries who have received funding under the grant must grant access to their results – on a royalty-free basis – to the granting authority, EU institutions, bodies, offices or agencies for developing, implementing and monitoring EU policies or programmes. Such access rights do not extend to beneficiaries' backgrounds. Such access rights are limited to non-commercial and non-competitive use. For actions under the cluster 'Civil Security for Society', such access rights also extend to national authorities of EU Member States for developing, implementing and monitoring their policies or programmes in this area. In this case, access is subject to a bilateral agreement to define specific conditions ensuring that:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• the access rights will be used only for the intended purpose and</i> <i>• appropriate confidentiality obligations are in place.</i> 	<p>IRISCC Grant Agreement</p>

	<i>Moreover, the requesting national authority or EU institution, body, office or agency (including the granting authority) must inform all other national authorities of such a request.</i>	
Access rights for the granting authority, Euratom institutions, funding bodies or the Joint Undertaking Fusion for Energy – Euratom actions	<i>In Euratom actions, the beneficiaries who have received funding under the grant must grant access to their results – on a royalty-free basis – to the granting authority, Euratom institutions, funding bodies or the Joint Undertaking Fusion for Energy for developing, implementing and monitoring Euratom policies and programmes or for compliance with obligations assumed through international cooperation with non-EU countries and international organisations. Such access rights include the right to authorise third parties to use the results in public procurement and the right to sub-license and are limited to non-commercial and non-competitive use.</i>	IRISCC Grant Agreement
Additional access rights	<i>Where the call conditions impose additional access rights, the beneficiaries must comply with them.</i>	IRISCC Grant Agreement
Background	<i>‘Background’ means any data, know-how or information – whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights – that is:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>a) held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement and</i> <i>b) needed to implement the action or exploit the results.</i> <i>If the background is subject to the rights of a third party, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that it can comply with its obligations under the Agreement.</i>	IRISCC Grant Agreement
Exploitation	<i>The use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.</i>	IRISCC Grant Agreement
Impacts	<i>Wider long-term effects on society (including the environment), the economy and science, enabled by the outcomes of R&I investments</i>	<u>European Commission</u>

	<i>(long term). It refers to the specific contribution of the project to the work programme's expected impacts described in the destination. Impacts generally occur sometime after the end of the project.</i>	Horizon Europe Guidelines [R4]
Innovation	<i>A new or changed entity, realizing or redistributing value. An entity is anything perceivable or conceivable, such as a product, service, process, model, method or a combination of thereof. They can be material, immaterial or imagined.</i>	ISO 56000 [R5]
	<i>The successful exploitation of new creations (inventions) which can be used to produce tangible benefits, satisfying needs and wants.</i>	Innovation Radar [R6]
Innovation Capacity	<i>Do the project results have the capacity to stimulate further innovations? Does it have the potential to be used in other areas or disciplines (beyond the project objectives)?</i>	Innovation Radar
Innovation Management	<i>The capability of management teams to transform novel technologies or research results into marketable products or services. The capacity to make the products or services accessible to a larger audience?</i>	Innovation Radar
	<i>Coordinated activities to direct and control an organization (project) concerning innovation</i>	ISO 56000
	<i>Management of all the activities related to understanding needs, with the objective of successfully identifying new ideas, and managing them, in order to develop new products and services which satisfy these needs.)</i>	IP Helpdesk [R7]
Innovation management system	<i>Set of interrelated or interacting elements of an Organization/Project to establish strategies, policies and objectives and Processes to achieve those objectives with regard to innovation.</i>	ISO 56000
Innovation Policy	<i>Intentions and direction of an organisation as formally expressed by its top management with regard to innovation.</i>	ISO 56000
Innovation Potential	<i>How much benefit (innovation) can the project results potentially deliver</i>	Innovation Radar
Innovation Strategy	<i>Plan to achieve objectives with regard to innovation</i>	ISO 56000
Intellectual Property (IP)	<i>Refers to creations/products of the mind, such as inventions, concepts, research & experimentation or products of creativity. Like</i>	IP Helpdesk Glossary [R8]

	<i>physical property, IP is an asset which can be traded (sold, bought, leased, used or given away), and is protected by law.</i>	
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)	<p><i>Is the legal right granted to IP owners to protect their IP, enabling people to earn recognition or financial benefit from what they invent or create. Some common types of IPR are:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright (Software, written works, engineering drawings Minimum viable products, prototypes, etc.) – it comes into existence automatically upon the creation of the original work • Patents (Technical inventions) – a monopoly right granted in return for causing the publication of an invention, preventing others to use it without agreement • Data from using rights (Creation & arrangement of data) – legal rights that protect the creation & management of data) • Design rights (Appearance) • Trademarks <p>Confidentiality Agreements (Know-how)</p>	IP Helpdesk Glossary
Key Exploitable Result (KER)	<i>A Key Exploitable Result (KER) is an identified main interesting result which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits – downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.</i>	European Commission Horizon Europe Guidelines
Objectives	<i>The goals of the work performed within the project, in terms of its research and innovation content. These will be translated into the project’s activities. These may range from tackling specific research questions, demonstrating the feasibility of innovation, and sharing knowledge among stakeholders on specific issues. The nature of the objectives will depend on the type of action and the scope of the topic.</i>	European Commission Horizon Europe Guidelines
Open Science	<i>An approach to the scientific process based on open cooperative work, tools and diffusing knowledge.</i>	AGA – Annotated

		<u>Grant Agreement EU Funding Programmes 2021-2027</u> [R9]
	<i>Open science is an approach to research based on open cooperative work that emphasizes the sharing of knowledge, results and tools as early and widely as possible. It is mandatory under Horizon Europe, and it operates on the principle of being 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'.</i>	<u>European Research Executive Agency – Open Science Guidelines</u> [R4]
Outcomes	The expected effects, over the medium term, of projects supported under a given topic. The results of a project should contribute to these outcomes, fostered in particular by the dissemination and exploitation measures (including the uptake, diffusion, deployment, and/or use of the project's results by direct target groups). Outcomes generally occur during or shortly after the end of the project.	European Commission Horizon Europe Guidelines
Ownership of results & Joint Ownership	<i>The granting authority does not obtain ownership of the results produced under the action.</i>	IRISCC Grant Agreement
Process	<i>Set of interrelated or interacting activities that use inputs to deliver an intended result.</i>	ISO 56000
Results	<i>'Results' means any tangible or intangible effect of the action, such as data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.</i>	IRISCC Grant Agreement
	<i>Everything that is generated during the project implementation. This may include, for example, know-how, innovative solutions, algorithms, proof of feasibility, new business models, policy recommendations, guidelines, prototypes, demonstrators, databases and datasets, trained researchers, new infrastructures, networks, etc. Most project results (inventions, scientific works, etc) are 'Intellectual Property', which may, if appropriate, be protected by formal 'Intellectual Property Rights</i>	European Commission Horizon Europe Guidelines

<p>Technology Readiness Levels (TRL)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRL 1 – basic principles observed • TRL 2 – technology concept formulated • TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept • TRL 4 – technology validated in the lab • TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies) • TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies) • TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in an operational environment • TRL 8 – system complete and qualified • TRL 9 – the actual system is proven in an operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or space) 	<p>European Commission Annex G. Grant Agreement [R10]</p>
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2 Innovation Management System

Innovation management at IRISCC aims to give a methodical approach to opportunity identification and validation, transforming it into knowledge that can be put into practice to improve the project's capacity to raise the effect of the solutions that are developed.

The Innovation Management System is implemented following a structured and operational approach aligned with ISO 56000 principles and inspired by best practices from Horizon Europe projects. In particular, the system is organised around clearly defined processes and associated procedures, including detailed steps, responsibilities, inputs, outputs, and validation mechanisms.

The system is designed to ensure that all project results are systematically captured, assessed, and progressively refined towards exploitation and impact.

Feedback originating from exploitation activities, stakeholder engagement, dissemination activities, periodic reporting, and governance reviews is systematically incorporated into the innovation management processes to support the continuous refinement of project results, KERs, sustainability plans, and impact pathways.

The innovation management processes are integrated with the project's reporting, dissemination, monitoring, and exploitation activities. Outputs generated through the different processes contribute to periodic reports, DEC strategy updates, KER catalogues, exploitation and sustainability analyses, and impact monitoring activities.

This integrated approach enables continuous improvement throughout the project lifecycle and ensures that innovation management activities are operationally embedded within the project governance structure rather than implemented as parallel activities.

The following are only a few examples of how the opportunities may be related:

- Identifying stakeholders' and customers' needs for fresh additions or the creation of new services while maintaining current ones (service innovation).
- Reaching out to new markets through community outreach.
- Project's internal operations (such as process innovation that improves the efficiency of the project's execution).
- Interfaces (such as novel use cases, pilots, demonstrators, experiments or cooperation models) with the user and provider communities.
- Interfaces between users or stakeholders' communities, such as those that help them collaborate.
- Identify key elements and practices that would support project operations (Project innovation)

2.1 The structure of the system

Figure 1. ISO 56000-based Innovation Management System.

The Figure 1 represent the overall structure of the Innovation Management System as per ISO 56000 standard. The primary steps outlined by the standard are as follows:

- Find Opportunities: This entails locating avenues for innovation by examining market trends, consumer demands, and other pertinent aspects. Ensuring that the innovation efforts are concentrated on areas with the greatest potential for impact and return on investment requires taking this crucial step.
- Create Concepts: Coming up with ideas and concepts for new goods, services, or procedures comes next after opportunities have been found. To develop a variety of potential concepts, this incorporates ideation sessions, brainstorming, and other creative activities.
- Validate Concepts: Validating concepts comes after they have been generated. This entails assessing the concepts, considering factors like consumer needs, market potential, technical viability, and alignment with corporate objectives. Methods, including market research, feasibility studies, and prototyping, can be used for validation.
- Develop Solutions: Following concept validation, solutions need to be developed. This includes creating and developing the good or service, testing and improving it, and getting it ready for use.
- Deploy Solutions: Implementing solutions is the last stage of the innovation management process. This entails introducing the good or service to the market, keeping an eye on its performance, and adjusting as needed.

2.2 The structure of the plan

The three primary tasks stated below, which must be completed throughout the project, form the foundation of the innovation management plan, together with the associated protocols and guidelines:

- To give the required market full information to incorporate into the project solutions, it is imperative to have a thorough understanding of the project's technological, political, societal and market context.
- Record and categorise project outcomes to advance innovations and services into the marketplace and policies.
- Create, track, and revise strategies for sustainability, exploitation, and business to guarantee that project outcomes are appropriately incorporated into anticipated effect pathways and to provide the required feedback loop to all other project innovation phases.

2.3 Supporting Tools and Infrastructure

The Innovation Management System is supported by a shared digital workspace hosted in the project collaborative environment (IRISCC Teams/SharePoint space), which acts as the internal central repository for all project-related activities and documentation. This environment ensures structured information management, traceability, and accessibility across the consortium. Within this structure, the Innovation Management folder is specifically designed to support all processes related to innovation and exploitation activities during the project's lifetime. It includes:

- IP Registry, where intellectual property (background, sideground, third-party, and foreground) is recorded and maintained;
- KER Registry, containing the list of Key Exploitable Results and their associated information;
- Templates Repository, including standardised templates for results, KERs, IP management, exploitation, and impact tracking.

This structured environment enables all project partners to contribute to and access up-to-date information. Version control mechanisms ensure traceability of changes, while access rights are managed according to project roles. Work Package leaders are responsible for providing and updating content, KER Champions maintain KER-related information, and the Innovation Manager oversees validation and coordination.

2.4 Innovation Management Timeline and Review Cycle

This section outlines the execution timeline of the Innovation Management Plan throughout the IRISCC project lifecycle, highlighting the major reporting activities, governance reviews, and expected updates related to Project Results, Intellectual Property (IP), Key Exploitable Results (KERs), exploitation activities, sustainability analyses, and impact monitoring. *Figure 2* represents the overall timeline, which complements the operational processes described in Chapter 4 and illustrates how innovation management activities are continuously reviewed, updated, and refined during the 54-month project duration.

M1–M6 – Innovation Management Setup and Governance Establishment

- Establishment of the Innovation Management framework and governance structure
- Identification of Background IP and access conditions
- Setup of registries and collaborative environment
- Initial stakeholder engagement and DEC activities
- Definition of innovation management procedures and responsibilities
- Initial project governance and coordination activities

Main related deliverables and milestones:

- D1.2 DEC Strategy (M5)
- D1.3 Innovation Management Plan (M6)
- MS6 IRISCC bodies established and project launched

M7–M12 – Initial Results Collection and Service Validation

- First collection of Project Results and IP-related information
- Initial identification of candidate KERs
- Review of exploitation opportunities and dependencies
- Validation of initial services, interoperability, and catalogue releases
- Refinement of stakeholder mapping and user requirements
- Initial contribution to continuous reporting activities

Main related deliverables and milestones:

- D1.4 Detailed stakeholder analysis (M12)
- D6.5 Accessibility of IRISCC services through EOSC federated AAI (M12)
- D7.2 Strategic IRISCC Access Programme (M12)
- D8.1 Optimized IRISCC TA management tool (M12)
- MS17 First online Catalogue release

M13–M24 – KER Consolidation and Exploitation Refinement

- Continuous update of Results and KER registries
- Consolidation and prioritisation of candidate KERs
- Refinement of exploitation pathways and sustainability analyses

- Integration of stakeholder and governance feedback
- Contribution to periodic reporting and DEC updates
- Monitoring of service uptake and onboarding activities

Main related deliverables and milestones:

- D1.5 IRISCC Policy Brief I (M18)
- D2.1 Overall co-design of SDLs and service concept (M18)
- D1.6 Updated DEC Strategy (M24)
- D2.2 Mapping of users' needs and requirements (M24)
- D3.2 Report from training activities Part I (M24)
- MS30 Established SDLs (M24)

M25–M36 — Mid-Term Innovation Review and Maturation

- Review and validation of mature KERs
- Assessment of innovation uptake and exploitation readiness
- Refinement of sustainability and impact activities
- Monitoring of interoperability and onboarding progress
- Consolidation of impact indicators and exploitation priorities
- Continuous update of innovation-related registries and reporting

Main related deliverables and milestones:

- D4.9 Report on DEMO maturity level for inclusion to Catalogue (M36)
- D6.9 Future integration and service recommendations (M36)
- D1.8 IRISCC Policy Brief II (M36)
- MS38 Intermediate report of virtual user workshops access provision (M36)

M37–M48 — Exploitation Consolidation and Sustainability Planning

- Consolidation of exploitation activities and service uptake
- Refinement of sustainability and long-term adoption strategies
- Update of innovation monitoring and impact assessment activities
- Continuous review of KERs and exploitation opportunities
- Validation of interoperability and EOSC integration activities

Main related deliverables and milestones:

- D2.4 Reports on service test phases (M48)
- D6.10 Interoperability and EOSC exchange report (M48)
- D7.5 Third release of IRISCC Catalogue of services (M48)
- MS41 Knowledge Services ready from SDLs (M48)

M49–M54 — Final Innovation Consolidation and Impact Assessment

- Final consolidation of Project Results and KERs
- Final update of exploitation and sustainability plans
- Assessment of innovation impact and long-term uptake
- Consolidation of success stories and final innovation portfolio
- Final contribution to governance and reporting activities
- Finalisation of sustainability and impact monitoring activities

Main related deliverables and milestones:

- D1.9 IRISCC Policy Brief III (M54)
- D3.5 Sustainability plan for training (M54)
- D5.3 Report assessing experiences on co-designed Knowledge Services (M54)
- D8.4 Final report and assessment of access provision and usage (M54)
- D11.3 Final DMP (M54)
- D11.5 Governance report (M54)

IRISCC – Innovation Management Plan Timeline (54 Months)

Innovation management activities are continuously reviewed and updated throughout the project lifecycle during reporting activities, governance meetings, deliverable submissions, and whenever significant innovation developments, exploitation opportunities, or IP-related changes emerge.

Figure 2. Innovation Management Plan Timeline

Innovation management activities are continuously reviewed and updated throughout the project lifecycle during reporting activities, governance meetings, deliverable submissions, and whenever significant innovation developments, exploitation opportunities, or IP-related changes emerge.

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3 Innovation Management Plan and Main Activities

3.1 Capturing and Identifying Project Results

A typical innovation funnel used to record outcomes in Horizon Europe Projects is shown in Figure 3. There are four stages to it:

- Identification of any background information, outside expertise, technology, and concepts that existed prior to the project's start and are required for its execution and/or exploitation.
- Determining project outcomes and ranking key outcomes.
- Identification of Important Exploitable Outcomes, including the primary routes of exploitation and commercial prospects.
- Identification of Project Innovations

Figure 3. Innovation Funnel for the identification of Project

Background had been identified during the negotiation phase of the IRISCC Consortium Agreement, where each partner was required to specify the access conditions for both

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implementation and exploitation. Access rights were further detailed within the Consortium Agreement. The relevant template used for documenting Background is provided in annex 8.1: Template for Background. Additional project-relevant information includes clarifying why the Background is needed, in which activities it is used (under which Work Package and Task), which partners require access, and whether dependencies exist with third-party technologies or anticipated Foreground.

Project Results are produced throughout the project implementation (see Figure 4). These may include, among others, Know-how, Guidelines, Prototypes, Demonstrators, Databases and Datasets, New Infrastructures, Policy Recommendations, Reports, Services, and Publications.

Figure 4. Results' Definition and Types

Main Results are those outputs prioritised by each partner due to their potential for exploitation. Exploitation can occur either within the context of project-developed technologies, linked to a Key Exploitable Result, or independently by the partner through other avenues.

Both Project Results and Main Results are recorded in a Results Register, as outlined in the template for Project Results (annex 8.2). The information collected for each result supports all parties involved in KER and IP management activities provides the necessary basis for completing the Results Ownership List required for continuous reporting in the EC Funding and Tenders portal. Key elements include the ownership of each result, whether held by a single partner or jointly by multiple partners, and the existence of any joint ownership agreements. Additional details cover the applicable IP protection mechanisms, including associated Intellectual Property Rights, the expected access conditions (open or proprietary, and under which licence), and any dependencies on third-party technologies, anticipated Foreground, or links to a Key Exploitable Result (KER).

KER represent the consortium-level results from a dissemination and exploitation perspective and are typically composed of the project's most relevant outputs. To further refine and consolidate these results, in IRISCC each KER is assigned a KER Champion, who

serves as the main point of contact for all matters related to that KER. The KER Champion supports coordination, promotes exploitation and dissemination activities, and acts as the primary spokesperson for the KER. This role also includes reviewing, proposing improvements, and validating KER-related documentation, promotional materials, and plans in collaboration with the relevant work package teams. Each KER is linked to specific exploitation pathways to ensure its uptake and sustainability beyond the project.

Template for KERs provides the structure for documenting KER and includes all the information required for their submission to the Horizon Results Platform (see annex 8.3). It includes a comprehensive description of the results achieved during the project, including the Technology Readiness Level (TRL), target groups, and expected exploitation pathways.

Innovations refer to those KERs and Results that have successfully progressed in their exploitation and demonstrate strong potential to generate impact on the market and society. The information collected by KERs and IPs management involved parties follows the European Commission's Innovation Radar methodology, with the aim of supporting the uptake and visibility of key innovations. Emphasis is placed on sustainability aspects, including Ownership, Access conditions, Maintenance and support, Costs, and expected return. The corresponding template is provided in the Template for Project Innovations, annex 8.4.

3.2 Exploitation Management

According to the IRISCC Grant Agreement definition, exploitation is the use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities. Therefore, furthering the use of the project's output in either non-commercial or commercial contexts can be considered exploitation.

Exploitation paths are defined, in the Grant Agreement, as 3 Pillars activities that will generate the project outputs, including IRISCC's KERs. These pillars are:

- Pillar I: User and stakeholder engagement (implementing IRISCC objectives 1, 2 and 5, through WP1, 2 and 3)
- Pillar II: Service integration (implementing IRISCC objectives 3 and 4, through WP4, 5 and 6)
- Pillar III: Service provision (implementing IRISCC objectives 1, 2, 3 and 5, through WP3, 7, 8, 9 and 10).

Additionally, the project's pathways toward impact are useful for integrating the pillars of the exploitation strategy. These pathways define expected outcomes as:

- Scientific
- Economic/Technological
- Societal

To exploit the results of the project we can define two types of exploitation:

- Commercial
- Non-Commercial

There are several types of tasks that can be customised based on the target audience. For example, the private sector may use data and services to develop tailored applications for end users or advance new equipment and products. Public authorities, on the other hand, might focus on leveraging IRISCC results to inform policy, practice, and decision-making processes. Research entities can use these results to achieve further scientific breakthroughs. The following tasks can be adapted according to the needs of each target group:

- Promoting IRISCC services to ensure visibility and adoption across sectors.
- Providing training for inter- and transdisciplinary users to enable effective utilization of IRISCC tools and data.
- Engaging and interacting with users and stakeholders to gather feedback, ensure relevance, and drive user-centred development.
- Networking with national, European, and international research and innovation activities to foster collaboration, particularly in addressing climate change risks.

These tasks are essential for ensuring the effective dissemination, exploitation, and sustained impact of IRISCC innovations, while their customisation allows for better alignment with the specific goals and needs of different sectors.

The foundations of these activities arise from the following reasons:

- The provision of cross-RI services explicitly supports the interdisciplinary research necessary to tackle the societal challenges caused by climate change risks.
- To build a climate-resilient Europe, scientific knowledge production needs to be based on interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches.

Moreover, following the importance of Open Science, the project relies on several practices related to it:

- Open Data: Several digital services in the IRISCC Catalogue of Services will utilize the existing data repositories, giving access to open data and derived data products. These repositories are managed and operated by RIs and offer structured discovery and access by metadata. The newly planned services will generate derived data products, which also will be managed by the RIs in repositories for giving open access, including provenance metadata on the used input data, analytical steps, and resulting output. Moreover, the aim of the IRISCC Catalogue of Services is to be shared and made available through a Marketplace that will be chosen, reaching out to a wider group of researchers.
- Open Applications: The IRISCC Catalogue of Services will include and give access to the new integrated and cross-disciplinary services, Demonstrators and Service Design Labs, that are made available as open applications, ready to be used and

re-used or extended, fostering knowledge exchange and re-usability of applications.

- Open Access: Besides providing open access to the data repositories, analytical services, and physical installations, the IRISCC project will provide user support in the form of training and technical consultancy for researchers who wish to make use of these systems.
- Open Knowledge: Scientific papers will be published at open, peer-reviewed publications enabling distribution through open repositories and shared also through the specifically developed Marketplace. Relevant documents from the project (e.g., public deliverables) will be shared in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/iriscc>) [R11]. This way, the transfer and uptake by researchers, both internal and external, will be strengthened.
- Data Management Plan (DMP): The project commits to the FAIR principles (data should be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) and adheres to ethical guidelines. Project's preliminary DMP designated as Deliverable D11.2 serves as the basis for IRISCC DMP living document to be updated over the course of the project. The final DMP will be presented as Deliverable D11.3 at the end of the project.

Developing exploitation management templates offers a methodical way to guarantee that innovations and important project results are efficiently utilised. These templates provide a standardised structure for recording, evaluating, and organising the project outcomes. Those templates can be found in the appendixes (annex 8.1-8.4).

3.3 IPR Management

The open-access conditions refer to a few different scenarios in which intellectual property (IP), including publications, data, and innovations, is shared:

- Repositories & Publications: Publications related to the project must go through the partners before they are publicly released. However, enough IPR must be safeguarded for open access, suggesting that once approved, publications should be accessible to the public freely through open-access repositories. The exact type of license for these publications would depend on what is agreed upon in the Consortium Agreement. Common open-access licenses are CC BY (Creative Commons Attribution), which allows sharing and adaptation with attribution, and CC BY-NC-ND (Non-Commercial, No Derivatives), which restricts commercial use and derivative works.
- Services & Digital Platforms: For access to digital services and platforms (such as datasets, tools, and models), the management of access rights, privacy, IPR, and licensing will be handled as part of the project. While it's not explicit, open access here likely refers to the principle of making these digital tools available royalty-free, at least for non-commercial research purposes. The specific license applied could vary based on what is allowed in the agreement, but it would likely involve non-commercial provisions such as CC BY-NC and others.

- **Physical Installations:** Access to background IP needed to complete project tasks will be royalty-free, suggesting that physical assets necessary for research might also be shared on a similar non-commercial basis. For training materials, the Consortium Agreement would likely define the licensing terms.
- **Access to data:** If the users submit their data resulting from access to the Data Centre, the Users shall grant to the project a worldwide, free-of-charge, perpetual, transferable, non-exclusive right to use the data and related documents generated by them within the Physical, Remote, or Virtual access for any purpose. This right includes, but is not limited to, the right to modify, reproduce, sublicense, and incorporate into other data, databases, or tools, as well as produce new developments. For justified and legitimate reasons, exceptions to the expected access rights may be allowed, for example, when the use of the results by the project could jeopardise a potential industrial/commercial use, violate the rules on personal data protection or confidentiality for security reasons, or for any other legitimate reason. Such exceptions must be agreed upon in writing on a case-by-case basis. Access rights to Background and Side-ground are agreed upon separately in writing.
- **Training Materials Licensing:** Regarding the license for training materials, the text implies that access to non-commercial research will be royalty-free, which is typically compatible with a license like CC BY-NC-ND. This would allow others to use and share the materials for non-commercial purposes, without modifying them, and with proper attribution to the creators.

Furthermore, licensing a particular kind of "exploitation agreement" (like a transfer agreement) can require identifying the intellectual property assets involved and the access restrictions attached to them.

The process of managing intellectual property (IP) is standardised by creating templates, which can be found in annexes 8.2.3 IPR Information and 8.4.4 IPR & Exploitation. These templates promote efficiency and uniformity in all IP-related endeavours.

3.4 Sustainability Management

Project sustainability refers to the ability to maintain, support, and further develop the project's major goals, services, results, and exploitation outcomes beyond the duration of the funded project. This includes ensuring that the training modules, thematic services, and other key assets developed during the project can continue to operate, evolve, and generate value after the end of the original funding period, without relying exclusively on project-specific financial support. Sustainability activities are nevertheless initiated and progressively refined throughout the project lifecycle in order to prepare for the long-term uptake, maintenance, and exploitation of the project results.

Specialised offerings about the primary goals of the project are sometimes referred to as thematic services (e.g., research tools, data platforms, analytical services, etc.). Finding

alternate business models that can increase revenue or save expenses is necessary to ensure the long-term viability of these services. Sustainable planning is also required for the services and training modules created during the project. For these, substitute models might guarantee that training stays current, relevant, and accessible. That said, even while generating income is essential to sustainability, certain training materials or theme services might need to be kept available for non-commercial uses, especially in the public or academic sectors. Managing the expected effort (manpower) and cost for user assistance, training, and technical consultancy can be made from a sustainability perspective, particularly concerning cost-benefit analysis.

A standardised approach that guarantees uniform procedures across diverse sustainability efforts is established by developing a template for sustainability management which can be found in annex 8.3.5 Your result's contribution to Sustainable Development.

3.5 Impact Management

The project's advancement of knowledge, technology, and education is ensured by the Scientific Impact. Competitiveness, expansion, and job creation are all fuelled by the economic impact. Finally, the Societal Impact guarantees that the project tackles societal issues, raises standards of living and promotes long-term sustainability. To convince the European Commission of the project's worth and to secure more money, all these effects are crucial. The scientific, economic, and societal impacts are crucial to demonstrate how the project benefits the broader community, economy, and scientific community.

A project impact canvas will be created after conducting workshops with all partners involved in managing the work packages, to clarify the processes and Key Exploitable Results (KERs) outlined in this document. This canvas will serve as a guide for documenting the KERs, while also considering the pathways of impact. It will assist in identifying Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that will be developed to evaluate the three types of impact: scientific, economic, and societal.

4 Innovation Management Processes

This section describes the innovation management processes and their associated procedures, following a structured approach that includes triggers, step-by-step activities, roles and responsibilities, and expected inputs and outputs. Each process is designed to ensure consistent execution across the consortium and to support traceability, validation, and continuous improvement.

All innovation management activities are continuously monitored throughout the project lifecycle. Reviews are performed during major reporting activities, governance meetings, and key deliverable submissions. Updates to registries, KERs, exploitation plans, sustainability analyses, and impact indicators are coordinated by the Innovation Manager with support from WP Leaders and KER Champions. Validated updates are maintained within the project SharePoint environment to ensure traceability, consistency, and alignment across activities.

Project Results identified through the Results Management process are assessed and prioritised as Main Results and candidate KERs. Selected KERs are further developed through exploitation and sustainability activities, while Impact Management monitors their contribution to project objectives, expected outcomes, and long-term impacts.

4.1. Intellectual Asset Inventory Management

Intellectual Asset Inventory Management is the first step in the innovation management process. This process, as detailed in Table 3 - Intellectual Asset Inventory Management Process Description, documents and maintains intellectual property (IP) created during the project (such as Background, Third-Party, and Result IP) as well as IP that existed before the project's inception and is pertinent to its execution and exploitation.

Table 3. Intellectual Asset Inventory Management Process Description

	Description
Process	Intellectual Asset Inventory Management
Process Manager	Innovation Manager
Leading Task	T1.4 Innovation Management and Exploitation

Description	This process documents and maintains the information related to the Intellectual Property (IP) including Ownership and Intellectual Property Rights, created during the project (such as Background, Third-Party, and Result IP) as well as IP that existed before the project's inception and is pertinent to its implementation and exploitation.										
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and record Background IP, Third-party IP, Foreground IP, and Result IP. • Make sure enough rights are in place for Background IP, Third-party IP, and Background IP. • Ensure project partners owning Result IP utilise appropriate protection mechanisms and facilitate the resolution of any IP conflicts that may arise. • Develop any IP agreements related to the generated IP (e.g. joint ownership, licensing, etc.) as described in the IPR Management section of this document. 										
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work programme, Grant Agreement, DoA, Consortium Agreement. • Deliverables, Milestones, Periodic Reports and WP reports. • Discussions with WP leaders, task leaders, consortium members, and different project boards. • Result IP and Key Exploitable Results (KERs). 										
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Templates and usage instructions for recording and documenting. Background IP, Third-party IP, Foreground IP, and Result IP, and Result IP. • List of project Background IP, Third-party IP, Foreground IP, and Result IP, and Result IP. • Joint ownership. 										
Activities for the process execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity 1: Record Background IP, Third-party IP, Foreground IP, and Result IP, and Result IP, in addition to iteratively reviewing and updating information and templates as needed. • Activity 2: Analyse the need for joint ownership and licensing agreements. • Activity 3: Draft and propose joint ownership. 										
Entities Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation Manager • WP Leaders/Task Leaders • Consortium Members • Executive Board 										
Triggers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project start • New IP identified • Need for IP protection • Joint ownership discussions 										
Steps	<table border="1" data-bbox="491 1960 1374 2000"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="491 1960 560 2000">#</th> <th data-bbox="560 1960 762 2000">Responsible</th> <th data-bbox="762 1960 1054 2000">Action</th> <th data-bbox="1054 1960 1374 2000">Output</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			#	Responsible	Action	Output				
#	Responsible	Action	Output								

	1	Innovation Manager	Prepare IP templates and guidelines	Templates and instructions for IP documentation
	2	Consortium Members	Identify Background and IP elements	List of Background, Third-party and Result IP
	3	Innovation Manager	Review and validate inputs	Validated IP information
	4	Innovation Manager	Identify ownership and dependencies	Ownership and dependency mapping
	5	Executive Board	Validate and resolve conflicts	Approved ownership and resolved conflicts
	6	Innovation Manager	Update IP register	Updated IP Registry
Checkpoints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The submission of the deliverables • The submission of periodic reports/participation at project reviews • Upon dissemination and communications and exploitation needs 			

4.2 Result IP Management

All results produced during the project's duration are tracked and managed via the process explained in Table 4 with a focus on KER-related findings. The process is driven by the objective to maximise uptake and minimise barriers to the adoption, adaptation and reuse of its project results. The process activities are coordinated by the Innovation Manager in collaboration with WP Leaders and consortium partners. Some activities may be delegated to relevant Work Packages, particularly for interactions related to specific IP assets, technical results, and exploitation activities.

Table 4. Result IP Management Process Description

	Description
Process	Results Management
Process Manager	Innovation Manager
Leading Task	T1.4 Innovation Management and Exploitation
Description	All results produced during the project's duration are tracked and managed via this process, with a focus on KER-related findings.

Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure that innovation developed or enhanced by the project is well-documented. • Provide a strong source of information for all other Innovation Management processes. • Identify, record, and manage project results in a template compatible with the Horizon Europe Results ownership list. 																												
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grant Agreement, DoA (Description of action), Consortium Agreement. • Deliverables, Milestones, Periodic Reports and WP reports. • Discussions with WP leaders, task leaders, consortium members, and different project boards and external parties. 																												
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Procedure and template to identify, record, and manage project results. • List of project results. 																												
Activities for the process execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity 1: Identify, record and manage results, in addition to iteratively reviewing and updating information and templates as needed. 																												
Entities Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation Manager • WP Leaders / Task Leaders • Consortium Members • Executive Board 																												
Triggers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New deliverable • New result identified • Reporting cycle 																												
Steps	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>#</th> <th>Responsible</th> <th>Action</th> <th>Output</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Innovation Manager</td> <td>Analyse deliverables and outputs</td> <td>Initial list of project results</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Innovation Manager</td> <td>Distribute results template</td> <td>Results template shared with partners</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Consortium Members</td> <td>Submit results information</td> <td>Completed results templates</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Innovation Manager</td> <td>Review and consolidate data</td> <td>Validated and consolidated results</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Executive Board</td> <td>Validate results</td> <td>Approved list of project results</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Innovation Manager</td> <td>Update Results Register</td> <td>Updated Results Register in SharePoint</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	#	Responsible	Action	Output	1	Innovation Manager	Analyse deliverables and outputs	Initial list of project results	2	Innovation Manager	Distribute results template	Results template shared with partners	3	Consortium Members	Submit results information	Completed results templates	4	Innovation Manager	Review and consolidate data	Validated and consolidated results	5	Executive Board	Validate results	Approved list of project results	6	Innovation Manager	Update Results Register	Updated Results Register in SharePoint
#	Responsible	Action	Output																										
1	Innovation Manager	Analyse deliverables and outputs	Initial list of project results																										
2	Innovation Manager	Distribute results template	Results template shared with partners																										
3	Consortium Members	Submit results information	Completed results templates																										
4	Innovation Manager	Review and consolidate data	Validated and consolidated results																										
5	Executive Board	Validate results	Approved list of project results																										
6	Innovation Manager	Update Results Register	Updated Results Register in SharePoint																										
Checkpoints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The submission of the deliverables • The submission of periodic reports/participation at project reviews 																												

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upon dissemination and communications and exploitation needs
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4.3 Key Exploitable Results Management

KERs are identified and prioritised based on criteria such as exploitation potential, Technology Readiness Level (TRL), identified target users or stakeholders, expected contribution to project impact, and sustainability potential beyond the project lifetime. KERs are reviewed during dedicated review meetings organised by the Innovation Manager, while final validation is performed by the Executive Board during major reporting activities and governance reviews. The prioritisation process considers exploitation readiness, strategic relevance, expected impact, sustainability potential, and alignment with project objectives.

All the data about Key Exploitable Results—results with a high potential for exploitation—is tracked and managed by the process described in Table 5.

Table 5. Key Exploitable Results Management Process Description

	Description
Process	Key Exploitable Results Management
Process Manager	Innovation Manager
Leading Task	T1.4 Innovation Management and Exploitation
Description	All the data about Key Exploitable Results—results with a high potential for exploitation—is tracked and managed by this process.
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designate KERs Champions and lay out guidelines for collaboration. • Identify, record, and manage KERs together with KERs Champions.
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grant Agreement, DoA, Consortium Agreement. • Deliverables, Milestones, Periodic Reports and WP reports. • Discussions with WP leaders, task leaders, consortium members, and different project boards.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Procedure and template to identify, record, and manage KERs. As part of the template, the value proposition and stakeholders for KER communications are collected. Information in this template will also allow for the later filling in of the Horizon Europe Results ownership and Results lists.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guideline for KER Champions. • List of KERs Champions. • List of KERs and related information. It will be refined and extended when the project results are more concrete. Similar related project results are grouped under a single KER. 																												
Activities for the process execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity 1: Record and manage information about KERs in collaboration with the KERs Champions, in addition to iteratively reviewing and updating information, guidelines, and templates as needed. 																												
Entities Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation Manager • WP Leaders/Task Leaders • Consortium Members • Executive Board 																												
Triggers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main results identified • TRL threshold reached • Exploitation opportunity 																												
Steps	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>#</th> <th>Responsible</th> <th>Action</th> <th>Output</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Executive Board</td> <td>Identify candidate KERs</td> <td>Initial list of candidate KERs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>WP Leaders</td> <td>Apply selection criteria</td> <td>Refined list of KERs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Executive Board</td> <td>Assign KER Champions</td> <td>List of assigned KER Champions</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Innovation Manager</td> <td>Complete KER templates</td> <td>Completed KER templates</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Executive Board</td> <td>Validate KERs</td> <td>Approved list of KERs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Innovation Manager</td> <td>Update KER register</td> <td>Updated KER Registry</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	#	Responsible	Action	Output	1	Executive Board	Identify candidate KERs	Initial list of candidate KERs	2	WP Leaders	Apply selection criteria	Refined list of KERs	3	Executive Board	Assign KER Champions	List of assigned KER Champions	4	Innovation Manager	Complete KER templates	Completed KER templates	5	Executive Board	Validate KERs	Approved list of KERs	6	Innovation Manager	Update KER register	Updated KER Registry
#	Responsible	Action	Output																										
1	Executive Board	Identify candidate KERs	Initial list of candidate KERs																										
2	WP Leaders	Apply selection criteria	Refined list of KERs																										
3	Executive Board	Assign KER Champions	List of assigned KER Champions																										
4	Innovation Manager	Complete KER templates	Completed KER templates																										
5	Executive Board	Validate KERs	Approved list of KERs																										
6	Innovation Manager	Update KER register	Updated KER Registry																										
Checkpoints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The submission of the deliverables • The submission of periodic reports/participation at project reviews • Upon dissemination and communications and exploitation needs 																												

4.4 Exploitation Management

Project partners can use Exploitation Management process to build an exploitation technique when developing their exploitation strategies, particularly for KERs. Exploitation options that can be pursued during or after the project to increase its impact are

discovered during this process, described in Table 6 – Exploitation Management Process Description. Commercial exploitation, product and process development, creation, manufacturing, marketing, service provision, and standardisation are examples of exploitation activities.

Table 6. Exploitation Management Process Description

	Description								
Process	Exploitation Management								
Process Manager	Innovation Manager								
Leading Task	T1.4 Innovation Management and Exploitation								
Description	Project partners can use this process to build exploitation practices when developing their exploitation strategies, particularly for Key Exploitable Results (KERs). Exploitation options that can be pursued during or after the project to increase its impact are discovered during this process. Commercial exploitation, product and process development, creation, manufacturing, marketing, service provision, and standardisation are examples of exploitation activities.								
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Propose a high-level exploitation strategy for the project results. Formulate a methodology and template to create partner-specific KER exploitation plans. Support the creation of Work Package-specific KERs exploitation plans (how each WP leader/KER champion plans to exploit the KERs). 								
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project results. KERs. Discussions with KERs Champions. 								
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High-level exploitation strategy for the project results. Work Packages' KERs exploitation plans. 								
Activities for the process execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activity 1: Support the creation of partner-specific KERs exploitation plans, in addition to iteratively reviewing and updating information and templates as needed. 								
Entities Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovation Manager WP Leaders/Task Leaders Consortium Members Executive Board 								
Triggers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KER identified Business opportunity Review meetings 								
Steps	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>#</th> <th>Responsible</th> <th>Action</th> <th>Output</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	#	Responsible	Action	Output				
#	Responsible	Action	Output						

	1	Innovation Manager & WP Leaders	Identify exploitation opportunities	List of exploitation opportunities
	2	Innovation Manager	Distribute exploitation template	Exploitation template shared
	3	Consortium Members	Define exploitation strategies	Draft KER exploitation plans
	4	Innovation Manager	Organise workshops	Workshop outcomes and refined strategies
	5	Executive Board	Validate strategies	Approved exploitation plans
	6	Innovation Manager	Monitor implementation	Updated exploitation progress information
Checkpoints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The submission of the deliverables • The submission of periodic reports/participation at project reviews • Upon dissemination and communications and exploitation needs 			

4.5 KERs Sustainability Management

The project partners, particularly those involved in KERs, can utilise the sustainability analysis approach defined in Table 7 to develop their sustainability plans. To maximise the project's impact, KERs Sustainability Management process also identifies sustainability options that can be explored during or after the project has ended.

Table 7. KERs Sustainability Management Process Description

	Description
Process	KER Sustainability Management
Process Manager	Innovation Manager
Leading Task	T1.4 Innovation Management and Exploitation
Description	The project partners, particularly those involved in KERs, can utilise the sustainability analysis approach defined by this process to develop their sustainability plans. To maximise the project's impact, it also identifies sustainability options that can be explored during or after it.

Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Formulate a methodology and create a template for partner-specific KERs sustainability analyses. Partner-specific KERs sustainability analyses. 																												
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Work programme, Grant Agreement, DoA, Consortium Agreement. Deliverables, Milestones, Periodic Reports and WP reports. Key Exploitable Results (KERs). Discussions with project partners. 																												
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partner-specific KERs sustainability analysis 																												
Activities for the process execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activity 1: Support Work Package Leaders in preparing Work Package sustainability analyses, and review and update templates iteratively as well as request updates as necessary. 																												
Entities Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovation Manager WP Leaders/Task Leaders Consortium Members Project Governance Bodies 																												
Triggers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KER maturity increase Mid-term review Final phase 																												
Steps	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>#</th> <th>Responsible</th> <th>Action</th> <th>Output</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Innovation Manager</td> <td>Define sustainability template</td> <td>Sustainability analysis template</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>KER Champions</td> <td>Identify sustainability options</td> <td>List of sustainability options</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Consortium Members</td> <td>Estimate costs and benefits</td> <td>Cost-benefit analysis</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Innovation Manager</td> <td>Consolidate plans</td> <td>Draft sustainability plans</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Executive Board</td> <td>Validate sustainability strategy</td> <td>Approved sustainability analyses</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Innovation Manager</td> <td>Monitor sustainability readiness</td> <td>Updated sustainability status</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	#	Responsible	Action	Output	1	Innovation Manager	Define sustainability template	Sustainability analysis template	2	KER Champions	Identify sustainability options	List of sustainability options	3	Consortium Members	Estimate costs and benefits	Cost-benefit analysis	4	Innovation Manager	Consolidate plans	Draft sustainability plans	5	Executive Board	Validate sustainability strategy	Approved sustainability analyses	6	Innovation Manager	Monitor sustainability readiness	Updated sustainability status
#	Responsible	Action	Output																										
1	Innovation Manager	Define sustainability template	Sustainability analysis template																										
2	KER Champions	Identify sustainability options	List of sustainability options																										
3	Consortium Members	Estimate costs and benefits	Cost-benefit analysis																										
4	Innovation Manager	Consolidate plans	Draft sustainability plans																										
5	Executive Board	Validate sustainability strategy	Approved sustainability analyses																										
6	Innovation Manager	Monitor sustainability readiness	Updated sustainability status																										
Checkpoints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The submission of the deliverables The submission of periodic reports/participation at project reviews Upon dissemination and communications and exploitation needs 																												

4.6 Impact Management

Impact Management process records information that will be used to assess the impact of the project per Horizon Europe recommendations. The impact is considered from three complementary perspectives: scientific, societal and economic. These different perspectives are recorded in pathways to impact and a brief impact canvas report (Table 8).

Table 8. Impact Management Process Description

	Description
Process	Impact Management
Process Manager	Innovation Manager
Leading Task	T1.4 Innovation Management and Exploitation
Description	This process records information that will be used to assess the impact of the project per Horizon Europe recommendations. The impact is considered from three complementary perspectives: scientific, societal and economic. These different views are recorded in pathways to impact and a brief impact canvas report.
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Document and update record the pathways to impact. • Document and update the impact canvas reporting template. The purpose of this template is to track and monitor the impact of different actions. It will include Specific needs, Expected results, D&E&C measures, Target groups, Outcomes, and Impacts, following the Horizon Europe recommendations. • Define a reporting template compatible with the Horizon Europe Results table. • Follow up exploitation activities after the end of the project. The first year after the end of the project, and if no exploitation takes place, beneficiaries must use a platform, (e.g. Horizon Results Platform) for making their exploitable results visible.
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work programme, Grant Agreement, DoA, Consortium Agreement. • Deliverables, Milestones, Periodic Reports and WP reports. • Project results and Key Exploitable Results (KERs). • Discussions with project partners and KERs ambassadors.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project pathways to impact. • Project impact canvas. • Impact metrics. • Impact reports.

Activities for the process execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activity 1: Continuously populate and update the project impact canvas in collaboration with project partners. Activity 2: Continuously follow up on impact and exploitation activities and report them as needed. 																								
Entities Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovation Manager WP Leaders/Task Leaders Consortium Members Executive Board 																								
Triggers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reporting cycle KPI update Stakeholder feedback 																								
Steps	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>#</th> <th>Responsible</th> <th>Action</th> <th>Output</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Consortium Members</td> <td>Define KPI framework (Proposal + GA)</td> <td>Defined KPIs aligned with GA and proposal</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Consortium Members</td> <td>Provide impact data</td> <td>Collected impact data</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Consortium Members</td> <td>Monitor KPIs</td> <td>Updated KPI tracking information</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Executive Board</td> <td>Validate impact data</td> <td>Validated impact data</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Innovation Manager</td> <td>Update impact reports</td> <td>Updated impact reports and impact canvas</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	#	Responsible	Action	Output	1	Consortium Members	Define KPI framework (Proposal + GA)	Defined KPIs aligned with GA and proposal	2	Consortium Members	Provide impact data	Collected impact data	3	Consortium Members	Monitor KPIs	Updated KPI tracking information	4	Executive Board	Validate impact data	Validated impact data	5	Innovation Manager	Update impact reports	Updated impact reports and impact canvas
#	Responsible	Action	Output																						
1	Consortium Members	Define KPI framework (Proposal + GA)	Defined KPIs aligned with GA and proposal																						
2	Consortium Members	Provide impact data	Collected impact data																						
3	Consortium Members	Monitor KPIs	Updated KPI tracking information																						
4	Executive Board	Validate impact data	Validated impact data																						
5	Innovation Manager	Update impact reports	Updated impact reports and impact canvas																						
Checkpoints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The submission of the deliverables The submission of periodic reports/participation at project reviews Upon dissemination and communications and exploitation needs 																								

5 Exploitation Results

Key Exploitable Results (KERs) are the specific outputs of a project that hold significant potential for future use. These could include new technologies, products, processes, methodologies, knowledge, or services that are innovative and can be exploited by stakeholders. The focus on KERs ensures that projects not only generate novel results but also translate those results into practical applications that deliver value.

Maximising a project's impact and sustainability is the advantage of recognising and controlling KERs. KERs make sure that important ideas are identified early on, developed methodically, and safeguarded for potential future use. In addition to improving the project's ability to address more general issues, this results in more chances for commercialisation, market entrance, and societal influence.

The KERs catalogue acts as an organised instrument for documenting the material and immaterial outcomes of a project that can be expanded upon, sold, or used to produce effects that go beyond the project's original parameters.

5.1 KERs Catalogue

The following tables, from Table 9 to Table 15 summarise the information associated with each identified KER.

The structure of each KER has the following content:

- Title
- KER Champion: chosen from the related Work Package leaders or Tasks leaders to better represent and manage the related activities.
- Related WP/Task: from which Work Package or Task the KER Champion was designed
Expected Outcomes Contributes
- Protection
- Target Audience
- Exploitation Path

Table 9. Key Exploitable Results #1 Details

KER 1 – Knowledge Services for Societal Use			
Services developed particularly to meet the needs of the non-academic users and service collaborators e.g., risk management platforms, and to ensure the rapid transition of scientific outputs to societal solutions.			
KER Champion	Related WP/Task	Expected Outcomes Contributes	Protection

EI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP2 • WP5 • WP6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #1 • #2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright for Documentation. • Copyright described in under open-source license for code • Trade Secret/Confidentiality in case of closed source.
Target Audience		Exploitation Path	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Societal users • Policymakers • Commercial users 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of the concept of Service Design Labs • Identifying users and key stakeholders for collaborative development of elaborated climate change risk services → as described in the stakeholders mapping and analysis (D.1.1) • Co-design Knowledge Services with users and stakeholders in four Service Design Labs (SDLs) including feedback-loop collection for service refinement. • Service testing and selecting a set of Knowledge Services with users and stakeholders for implementation • Evaluate maturity level including the definition of Service Policies addressing access conditions and legal arrangements necessary to meet societal, policy and commercial user requirements. 	

Table 10. Key Exploitable Result #2 Details

KER 2 – Scientific Services for R&I Actions			
Cross-RI climate change risk services for research communities, which particularly support European R&I actions, Mission on Climate adaptation and ERA objectives.			
KER Champion	Related WP/Task	Expected Outcomes Contributes	Protection
ACTRIS ERIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP4 • WP6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #1 • #2 • #4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EULAs
Target Audience		Exploitation Path	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-design the Demonstrators. • Optimise the Demonstrator design and key outputs. • Provide the necessary set of climate risk model outputs supporting the six Demonstrators. • Implement the six Demonstrators. 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate the maturity level and transferability of the Scientific Services created in the Demonstrators to the IRISCC Catalogue of services; in terms of practical activities, it means service policies in place, access conditions in place, and legal arrangements in place (e.g. EULAs).
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Table 11. Key Exploitable Result #3 Details

KER 3 – IRISCC Catalogue of services			
<p>Catalogue of services enables a single entry point to all IRISCC services. Catalogue of services gathers for the first time climate change risk-related RI services together. Key KER for supporting the successful exploitation of all the other KERs.</p>			
KER Champion	Related WP/Task	Expected Outcomes Contributes	Protection
UCPH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP6 WP7 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> #1 #2 #3 #4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creative Commons
Target Audience		Exploitation Path	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researchers Commercial users Societal users Policymakers 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-design across RIs, user communities and stakeholders, the metadata model, content, and suggested functionality, of the integrated IRISCC Catalogue of services enabling effective user access and utilisation of inter- and transdisciplinary approaches. Validate and enhance the integration and customisation of the IRISCC services enabling additional user functionality and approaches. Design a strategic Access Programme for optimal planning and implementation of the IRISCC access calls enabling users optimally to benefit from the integrated and customised climate change risk services. Ensure the long-term sustainability of the IRISCC Catalogue of services and service provision beyond the project lifetime. 	

Table 12. Key Exploitable Result #4 Details

KER 4 - Transnational (onsite and remote), virtual access, and hybrid access provision to IRISCC services.			
<p>VA, TA and combined hybrid access provision to research, innovation, training and digital services at the leading European and national RIs and their state-of-the-art observatories, experimental facilities, modelling, and data infrastructures in the field of climate and environmental sciences, health, and social sciences. Key KER for supporting the successful exploitation of all the other IRISCC KERs.</p>			
KER Champion	Related WP/Tasks	Expected Outcomes Contributes	Protection
CNR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP6 WP8 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> #1 #2 #3 #4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Policies Access Conditions Licenses for Technologies used (IP protection would be copyright - Creative Commons or described in OS License, Trade secret/Confidentiality for closed source, (or traditional IP protection such as patents) etc.
Target Audience		Exploitation Path	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researchers Commercial users 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement and operate the centralised, online Transnational Access management system Implement and operate the centralised Virtual Access management system Support for service users and service providers to ensure full onboarding Assess the performance of the centralized and integrated IRISCC access and service system 	

Table 13. Key Exploitable Result #5 Details

KER 5 - Modern and transferable RI and data stewardship skills to use research data and cutting-edge RIs and their services
<p>Online and onsite training for users to enable the optimal use of the leading RIs and increase European researchers' skills in data stewardship. Technical and scientific support is also given in conjunction with virtual access (help desk functions) and transnational onsite visits by service providers</p>

KER Champion	Related WP/Tasks	Expected Outcomes	Protection
UH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP3 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> #4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Policies Access Conditions Licenses for Technologies used (IP protection would be copyright - Creative Commons or described in OS License, Trade secret/Confidentiality for closed source, (or traditional IP protection such as patents) etc.
Target Audience		Exploitation Path	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researchers Commercial users 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop an inter-and transdisciplinary Training and Knowledge Exchange Plan for the IRISCC Ensure and implement capacity building in climate change risks through novel onsite and online training modules Foster the innovation capacity, harvesting from the Demonstrators Create a sustainable knowledge exchange and cross-RI training program. 	

Table 14. Key Exploitable Result #6 Details

KER 6: New adopted co-design RI approach to respond to challenge-driven service needs of societal actors			
Adoption of a new approach for developing novel RI services through co-design with service users and stakeholders to meet the challenge-driven scientific and societal knowledge production needs.			
KER Champion	Related WP/Tasks	Expected Outcomes	Protection
EI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> #1 #2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creative Commons
Target Audience		Exploitation Path	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Societal users Policymakers 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of the concept for co-designing IRISCC-integrated Knowledge Services 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commercial users • Key collaborators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying users and key stakeholders for collaborative development of elaborated climate change risk services • Co-design Knowledge Services with users and stakeholders in four Service Design Labs (SDLs)
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Table 15. Key Exploitable Result #7 Details

KER 7: Established model of sustainability for IRISCC services and challenge-driven cross-RI service provision.			
A proposed strategy and model for how to maintain the operational service provision of integrated services beyond the project lifetime. An established sustainability model can be applied to other multi-actor and challenge-driven RI service			
KER Champion	Related WP/Tasks	Expected Outcomes Contributes	Protection
EGI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • T1.4 • T7.4 • D3.5 • D7.6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #1 • #2 • #4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creative Commons
Target Audience		Exploitation Path	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers • Commercial users • Societal users • Policymakers • Key collaborators 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish a plan for the sustainability of the project in collaboration with the other partners of the consortium. 	

6 Conclusions

This deliverable outlines the main features of the IRISCC Innovation Management Plan, including its procedures, operational approach, governance structure, and implementation context. It defines the processes and responsibilities for identifying, reviewing, updating, and managing Project Results, Key Exploitable Results (KERs), Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), and access rights throughout the project lifecycle. The plan also covers the development of exploitation and sustainability activities, impact assessment, and the continuous monitoring and refinement of innovation-related information through reporting activities, governance reviews, and dedicated process updates. Expanding upon the information provided in the DoA, a baseline Exploitation Plan for IRISCC has been established together with an operational timeline for the execution and review of innovation management activities.

7 References

Reference	
No	Description/Link
1	Project Deliverable D1.1, Stakeholder mapping and analysis (ICOS ERIC, M3). Not public.
2	Project Deliverable D1.2, Dissemination Exploitation and Communication (DEC) strategy (EGI.eu, M5). https://zenodo.org/records/13458024
3	Request for Comment number 2119, on Best Current Practice https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc2119
4	Horizon Europe Programme Guide https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf
5	ISO 56002:2019 on Innovation management – Innovation management system – Guidance https://www.iso.org/standard/68221.html
6	Innovation Radar methodology https://www.innoradar.eu/methodology
7	Intellectual Property Helpdesk https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/index_en
8	European Commission – IP Glossary https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk/europe-glossary_en
9	Annotated Grant Agreement from the European Commission https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf
10	Open science in Horizon Europe https://rea.ec.europa.eu/open-science_en
11	Technology readiness levels (TRL) https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

12	Zenodo page for IRISCC Project https://zenodo.org/communities/iriscc
13	Sustainable Development Goals from the United Nations https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdgs

8 Annexes

8.1: Template for Background

According to the IRISCC Grant Agreement (Article 16.1) Background is defined as “any data, know-how or information (...) that is (...) needed to implement the Action or exploit the results”. Because of this need, Access Rights have to be granted in principle, but Parties must identify and agree amongst themselves on the Background for the Project. This is the purpose of this attachment.

NAME OF THE PARTY

As to NAME OF THE PARTY, it is agreed between the Parties that, to the best of their knowledge, the following Background is hereby identified and agreed upon for the Project. Specific limitations and/or conditions shall be as mentioned hereunder:

Describe Background	Specific restrictions and/or conditions for implementation (Article 16.4 Grant Agreement and its Annex 5, Section “Access rights to results and background”, sub-section “Access rights to background and results for implementing the Action”)	Specific restrictions and/or conditions for Exploitation (Article 16.4 Grant Agreement and its Annex 5, Section “Access rights to results and background”, sub-section “Access rights for exploiting the results”)
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8.2: Template for Project Results

8.2.1 Description

Name	<Name of the Project Result>
Description	<Describe the result in brief>
URL	<URL(s) to the result>
WPs and Tasks involved	<List all the Work Packages including Tasks involved in generating the result>

Result Type	<Select one of the following> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Related Results • Scientific or Technological R&D results (including HW) • ICT Software Digital Solution • Other Intangible Results • Services • Other
Result Contact Person	<Contact information of the primary contact person for the result>

8.2.2 Impact and Innovation

Innovation	<Describe what is new in the result. How it benefits the users and society in general>
Potential beneficiaries or customer groups	<Describe the potential user groups for the result. For each group describe, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • what is the exploitation/use objective for them? (e.g. use for further research, use for policy support, etc)? • What are the main messages you want to deliver? • What are the best channels to deliver messages? • How will the target group (when they hear your message and want to use the result(s)) access and use the results, and under what terms (i.e. who do they approach, where is the result located, etc)?>
Geographical Market	<Describe the local or global geographical regions for which the result has been developed primarily>

8.2.3 IPR Information

Are there IPR issues that will limit foreseen use?					
IP Background	<Please list all IP components related to the result brought by the partners into the project. This might be reports, software code, etc. There may be several IP components for each result. Don't forget know-how – which may be delivered as training or consultancy to support use.>				
	Name	Short Description	IP Owner	Type of protection or	Protection or licensing actions used

					licensing action used	

Third-party IPs	<Please list all IP third-party components for which IP is owned by organizations outside the project.>				
	Name	Short description	IP Owner	Type of protection or licensing action used	Protection or licensing actions used

IP Sideground	<Please list all IP components which are relevant to the project but produced outside the project by any of the partners during the project's tenure (providing a summary of the components of this aggregate result)>				
	Name	Short description	IP Owner	Type of protection or licensing action used	Protection or licensing actions used

IP Foreground	<Please list all IPs created during the project. Include all the IPs related to components of this result.>									
	Name	Short description	Partners Owner & Other Beneficiary(s) involved during the project	Related contribution of Partners involved during the project	Who will manage the IP (Host/Protect/Market/Exploit) and under what terms?	Confidential Click on YES/NO	Foreseen embargo date	Type of protection or licensing action used	Protection or licensing actions used	How costs and revenues will be decided and shared?
						Yes		Patents Trademarks Registered designs Utility models Others		
						No				

8.2.4 Dissemination

Early Adopters	<Briefly describe who are the early adopters>
Dissemination Channels	

8.3: Template for Key Exploitable Results

8.3.1 Results

Title of result (120 characters)	Ideally, a punchy name that makes sense to someone who hasn't heard about EOSC, e-Infrastructures or Cloud technologies. Writing acronyms (like EOSC) out might be a good idea.						
Message/ Teaser to the potential user (1000 characters)	<p>State what your result is, what it is for, what makes it special in terms of adding value or knowledge, what is your purpose for making it public, and what is your target audience.</p> <p>Use page "Five_Ws" on Wikipedia¹ as a support when drafting the text.</p>						
Video/ image section	Upload an image (primary goal: visually attractive item to draw attention and trigger curiosity) or add a link to a YouTube/Vimeo video.						
Result Type	<p>Select one from the following list,</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy Related Results </td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific or Technological R&D results (including HW) </td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICT Software Digital Solution </td> </tr> <tr> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other Intangible Results </td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Services </td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other </td> </tr> </table>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy Related Results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific or Technological R&D results (including HW) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICT Software Digital Solution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other Intangible Results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy Related Results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific or Technological R&D results (including HW) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICT Software Digital Solution 					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other Intangible Results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other 					
Target Audience	Select max three from the list,						

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Five_Ws

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Others/ No specific audience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public or private funding institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU and Member State Policy-makers
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research and Technology Organisations
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academia/ Universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private Investors 	
Our needs are	Select max three from the list,		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business partners - SMEs, Entrepreneurs , Large Corporations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incubators/ Accelerators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marketing Mentoring or Coaching
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financing Expertise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technology Transfer Expertise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal / IPR advise
	I/we wish to transfer my/our IPR to an interested party	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investor readiness training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investor introductions
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business plan development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expanding to more markets/finding new customers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Executive Training
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business Angels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Venture Capital 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crowd-funding Equity

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other types of Investment 		
We specifically need/ are looking for (600 words)	Freeform description of what the result owners are looking for (more specifically than the selection from the list) from the members of the target audiences selected.		

8.3.2 About us

Main project	An EC-funded project that was the main contributor
Other related projects	Optional – won't be visible in the entry
Result Contributors	The partners that contributed to the result.
Owners for exploitation	Partners that will serve as contact points for further exploitation. In case the business model is based on licensing of IPR, this needs more care (either a single owner or parties to a joint ownership agreement)
Start-up created for further exploitation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes No
Logo	Not applicable unless there's a startup in the works

8.3.3 Testimonials

Title	Title of the success story collection (should at least contain material that is not created by the contributors or owners). You can add several entries to this section (click Add information)
Link	URL

8.3.3 Find us on

Description	This could be e.g. homepage or other entry. As with testimonials, it is possible to add more than one line: homepage + marketplace entry ideal solution.
Link	URL

8.3.4 Results description and influence

Result description (1200 characters)	A more detailed description of the result, freeform.					
Business Sector(s)/ Policy Area(s)	Select max three from the list,					
	Agriculture and rural development	Banking and financial services	Borders and security	Budget	Business and industry	Climate action
	Competition	Consumers	Culture and media	Customs	Digital economy and society	Economy, finance and the euro
	Education and training; Employment and social affairs	Energy; Environment	EU enlargement	European neighbourhood policy	Food safety	Foreign affairs and security policy
	Fraud prevention	Home affairs	Humanitarian aid and civil protection	Institutional affairs	International cooperation and development	Justice and fundamental rights
	Maritime affairs and fisheries	Migration and asylum	Public health	Regional policy	Research and innovation	Single market
	Sport	Statistics	Taxation	Trade	Transport	Youth
Tags/ Keywords	Recommend that you use keywords to describe the technology, science, sector, content or nature of the result and very importantly, keywords to denote potential uses or applications of your result. Please note that, by default, you will see in your submission form all keywords linked to the main project you had chosen for declaring this result. This is to help you get started. Feel free to remove those keywords irrelevant to this result.					

8.3.5 Your result's contribution to Sustainable Development

Contribution to UN Sustainable Development Goals	Select max three from the list:			
	GOAL 1: No Poverty	GOAL 2: Zero Hunger	GOAL 3: Good Health and Well-being	GOAL 4: Quality Education

	GOAL 5: Gender Equality	GOAL 6: Clean Water and Sanitation	GOAL 7: Affordable and Clean Energy	GOAL 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth
	GOAL 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	GOAL 10: Reduced Inequality	GOAL 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities	GOAL 12: Responsible Consumption and Production
	GOAL 13: Climate Action	GOAL 14: Life Below Water	GOAL 15: Life on Land	GOAL 16: Peace and Justice Strong Institutions
	GOAL 17: Partnerships to achieve the Goal	Not Applicable		
Radical Innovation Breakthrough ?	(Optional) Is it a Radical Innovation Breakthrough?			
Are you a member of the 'World Alliance for 1000 Solutions'?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No 			

8.3.6 Your result's influence on policy

Has your result had or do you expect it to have a significant influence on policy-making?

- Yes
- No

8.3.7 Other information/data to share

Title (optional, one or more links to further information)

Open access publications, presentations, etc.

Link

URL

8.3.8 Result, Business Maturity and Exploitation Outlook

Result Maturity	TRL Level				
Current Stage and Next Steps	More details/justification of the maturity.				
Do you already have customers for this result?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No 				
Number of existing customers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1-5 • 6-30 • 31-50 • 51-100 • 101-500 • 501-1000 • >1000 				
What type of customers/users do you have?	Select all that are applicable,				
	Individuals	SMEs	Big corporations	Academia	R&T organisations
	Public Institutions and Authorities	Governments	Commerce	Manufacturers	
Which Business Sectors do your customers mainly come from?	Select all that are applicable,				
	Agriculture and rural development	Banking and financial services	Borders and security	Budget	Business and industry
	Climate action	Competition	Consumers	Culture and media	Customs
				Digital economy and society	Economy, finance and the euro

	Education and training; Employment and social affairs	Energy; Environment	EU enlargement	European neighbourhood policy	Food safety	Foreign affairs and security policy
	Fraud prevention	Home affairs	Humanitarian aid and civil protection	Institutional affairs	International cooperation and development	Justice and fundamental rights
	Maritime affairs and fisheries	Migration and asylum	Public health	Regional policy	Research and innovation	Single market
	Sport	Statistics	Taxation	Trade	Transport	Youth
Unique value proposition	The unique selling proposition (USP), also called the unique selling point, or the unique value proposition (UVP) in the business model canvas, is the marketing strategy of informing customers about how one's brand or product is superior to its competitors (in addition to its other values).					
Do you have a scalable business model?	For a business model to be scalable, staffing requirements should grow in a strongly sublinear fashion and/or the revenue per customer (or end-user) should remain relatively stable. Grant-based sustainability is usually not scalable, nor is consulting. Franchising, licensing and platform business models can be.					
Is your result replicable?	(Judgement call) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes ● No 					
Please elaborate on the Replicability	Justification for a claim for replicability.					
Is your result and your business model						

sustainable in the long term?	
Please elaborate on the Sustainability	Justification to claim the solution is sustainable.
Are you targeting geographical markets?	Geographical market areas, or can also be global.

8.3.9 Investor Corner

What level of investment (EUR) are you currently looking for?	Levels of funding sought: if a € sum is chosen.
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8.4: Template for Project Innovations

8.4.1 Innovations

INNOVATION 1 (optional)

1. Title of the innovation

Please enter a meaningful innovation title (between 20 and 200 characters, spaces included). This field will be revealed to the public on the Innovation Radar platform/mobile app.

Tip: This field is key and needs to be strong and clear. If possible, use a **'for'** clause. Examples of **poor versus good innovation titles:**

'Laser Design Platform' (poor) vs 'Improved semiconductor laser design platform for RWG (Ridge Wave Guide) laser' (good)

'Novel Robot Arm' (poor) vs 'Dextrous robotic slave arm **for** high radiation environments' (good)

*'Biosensors for diagnosis' (poor) vs 'Biosensors capable of breath and saliva monitoring **for** heart failure diagnosis' (good)*

2. Description of the innovation

Please describe the innovation. Use less than 500 characters, spaces included.

*This field will **NOT** be revealed to the public on the Innovation Radar platform/mobile app*

3. This innovation is ...

Under development

Already developed but is not yet being exploited

Being exploited

4. Characterise the type of innovation (choose one only)

Significantly improved product

Significantly improved service (except consulting services)

Significantly improved process

Significantly improved marketing method

Significantly improved organisational method

Consulting services

New product

New service (except consulting services)

New process

New marketing method

New organisational method

Other				
5. Level of Innovation: What is the level of innovation? (<i>choose one only</i>)				
Some distinct, probably minor, improvements over existing products				
Innovative but could be difficult to convert customers				
Innovative and easily appreciated advantages for the customer				
Very innovative				
6. How will the innovation be exploited? (<i>choose one only</i>)				
Introduced as new to the market (commercial exploitation)				
Only deployed as new to the organisation/company (new internal processes implemented, etc.)				
No exploitation planned				
If 'no exploitation planned' is selected, explain why not:				
[insert explanations]				
7. Indicate the step(s) to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market or to society				
<i>Answer the following grid only if the answer to the previous question is 'Introduced as new to the market' (choose only one answer per row)</i>				
	Done or ongoing	Planned	Not planned but needed or desirable	Not planned and not needed
Technology transfer				
A partner's research team and business units are both engaged in activities				

relating to this innovation				
Market study				
Prototyping in a laboratory environment				
Prototyping in a real-world environment				
Pilot, Experiment, Prototype, Demonstration or Testing activities				
Feasibility study				
Launch a start-up or spin-off				
Licensing the innovation to a 3rd party				
Complying with existing standards				
Contribution to standards				
Raise capital				
Raise funding from public sources				
Business Plan				
Other (please specify)				

If 'Other' is selected, please specify what other steps have been done or planned for this innovation:

[insert explanations]

8. Is there a clear 'owner' of the innovation in the consortium or multiple owners?

Only for multi-beneficiary projects

One clear owner

Multiple owners

9. Indicate (up to a maximum of 3) key organisation(s) delivering this innovation.

10. Indicate these organisations' needs to fulfil their market potential

	Organisation 1	Organisation 2	Organisation 3
Investor readiness training			
Investor introductions			
Biz plan development			
Expanding to more markets			
Legal advice (IPR or other)			
Mentoring or Coaching			
Partnership with other SME(s)			
Partnerships with large corporates			
Incubation/Startup accelerator			
Executive Training			
Other: Standardization efforts			

Further developments in a co-design approach through the common project			
11. For the private company/companies chosen as one of the 3 'key innovators', will this innovation be used by mainly current or new customers?			
Current customers			
New customers			
12. Market maturity: The market targeted by this innovation is ... (choose one only)			
The market does not yet exist, and it is not yet clear that the innovation has the potential to create a new market			
Market-creating: The market does not yet exist, but the innovation has clear potential to create a new market			
Emerging: There is a growing demand and few offerings are available			
Mature: The market is already supplied with many products of the type proposed			
13. Market dynamics: is the market ...? <i>Answer this question only if the answer to the previous question is 'mature'.</i>			
In decline			
Holding steady			
Growing			
14. Are there other markets for this innovation that the innovators are not yet targeting?			
Yes			
No			
15. Market competition: How strong is competition in the target market?			
Patchy, no major players			
Established competition but none with a proposition like the one under investigation			

Several major players with strong competencies, infrastructure and offerings
16. When do you expect that such innovation could be commercialised (from today)?
Less than 1 year
Between 1 and 3 years
Between 3 and 5 years
Between 5 and 10 years
More than 10 years
17. Has a trademark been registered for this innovation?
Yes
No
18. Which of the Societal Challenge(s) is/are the innovation relevant to?
Health, demographic change and well-being
Food security, sustainable agriculture, marine and maritime, Bioeconomy
Secure, clean and efficient energy
Smart, green and integrated transport
Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials
Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies
Secure societies - protecting the freedom and security of Europe and its citizens
Not relevant to any Societal Challenge
If 'not relevant to any SC is selected' explain why.
[insert explanations]
19. Which of the <u>UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)</u> [R13] does this innovation contribute to?
SDG 1 – No Poverty
SDG 2 – Zero Hunger
SDG 3 – Good Health and Well-being

SDG 4 – Quality Education
SDG 5 – Gender Equality
SDG 6 – Clean Water and Sanitation
SDG 7 – Affordable and Clean Energy
SDG 8 – Decent Work and Economic Growth
SDG 9 – Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure
SDG 10 – Reducing Inequity
SDG 11 – Sustainable Cities and Communities
SDG 12 – Responsible Consumption and Production
SDG 13 – Climate Action
SDG 14 – Life Below Water
SDG 15 – Life On Land
SDG 16 – Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions
SDG 17 – Partnerships for the Goals
Not relevant to any SDG
If 'not relevant to any SDG is selected' explain why.
[insert explanations]
20. Does this innovation have the potential to address climate mitigation or climate adaptation?
<i>Climate mitigation potential: The innovation addresses the causes of climate change (i.e. it can reduce and curb greenhouse gas emissions)</i>
<i>Climate adaptation potential: The innovation can reduce vulnerability to the harmful effects of climate change</i>
Mitigation potential
Not applicable to this innovation
Adaptation potential

8.4.2 Innovation Performance

Innovation Performance					
How do you consider the project's performance in terms of innovation?					
Performing below my expectations					
Meeting my expectations					
Exceeding my expectations					
Highly exceeding my expectations					
Does the innovator engage end-user organisations?					(Yes/No)
If 'Yes' to the previous question, are the end-users in the consortium?					(Yes/No)
If 'Yes' to the previous question; please indicate which project participant(s) are end-users and what their key contribution is					
	Providing Ideas	Testing	Validation	Deployment	Not an end-user
Participant A					
Participant B					
Participant C					
If 'No' to the previous, please indicate which types of organisations outside the consortium are engaged with and what is their key input as a user.					
	Providing Ideas	Testing	Validation	Deployment	Not consulted
Potential procurer of innovation (Public sector)					
Potential procurer of innovation (Private sector)					
Citizen Group					
NGO					

Innovation Performance					
How do you consider the project's performance in terms of innovation?					
Regulator					
Policy Maker					
Other					

8.4.4 IPR & Exploitation

IPR & Exploitation	
Are there IPR issues within the consortium that could compromise the ability of the organisation(s) to exploit new products/solutions/services, internally or in the marketplace?	(Yes/No)
Which are the external bottlenecks that compromise the ability of project partners to exploit new products, solutions or services, internally or in the marketplace?	
Regulation	
Skills in the wider workforce	
Standards	
Financing	
Trade issues (between MS, globally)	
IPR	
Others	
Indicate how many patents have been applied for by the project	
How would you rate the level of commitment of relevant organisation(s) to exploit the innovation?	
Very low	
Low	
Average	
High	

IPR & Exploitation	
Very High	
Please indicate the one participant (excluding large enterprises) that the panel considers to be the most impressive in terms of innovation potential within the context of the innovations identified	
(insert name of participant)	
Please provide concrete recommendations for the project to improve its innovations and their potential to deliver impact in - or close to - the marketplace.	
(insert recommendation)	
Hypothetically but honestly, would you invest your own money in any innovation developed by this project?	(Yes/No)
Please indicate the participant(s) from which a woman is in a position of leadership (such as Principal Investigator / Work Package Leader) for this project:	
(insert name of participant)	